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The Employment Rate in the Italian Regions

In 2019, the employment rate in the South was equal to -1.8% of the corresponding value in 2004.

Ranking of regions by occupancy rate. Istat calculates the employment rate. The employment rate is defined as the “[...] ratio between the employed and the corresponding reference population”. The data reported refer to 2019. In first place for employment rate is Trentino-Alto Adige with an employment rate value of 76.6 followed by Emilia Romagna with an employment rate of 75.4 and from the Aosta Valley with a value of 73.5. In the middle of the table there are the Marche with an employment rate of 69.8% followed by Umbria with an employment rate of 69.3% and Liguria with an employment rate of 67.7%. Calabria closes the ranking with an employment rate of 45.3%, followed by Campania with a value of 45.2% and Sicily with an amount equal to 44.5%.

Variation in the employment rate for the Italian regions between 2004 and 2019. The variation in the employment rate for the Italian regions between 2004 and 2019 sees Friuli-Venezia Giulia in first place with + 5.5%, followed by from Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of + 5.4% and from Tuscany with an amount of + 4.9%. In the middle of the table there are Emilia-Romagna with an amount equal to 3.7%, Lazio with an amount equal to + 2.9% and Valle d'Aosta with a value equal to 2.9%. Sicily closes the ranking which has reduced the employment rate by a value equal to 2.6%, Campania with a value equal to -4.2% and Calabria with an amount equal to -5.4%.

The trend of the employment rate in Northern Italy in the 2015-2019 period. In the North, the trend in the employment rate increased from an amount equal to 69.40% in 2015 to an amount equal to 70.60% in 2016 or a value equal to 1.20 points in absolute value and 1.73 % as a percentage. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of the employment rate in Northern Italy went from an amount equal to 70.60% to a value of 71.50% or equal to a change of 0.90 units in value absolute equal to a value of 1.27%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the employment rate in Northern Italy increased from an amount equal to 71.50% up to an amount equal to 72.205 or equal to a variation of 0.70 units in absolute and equal value to a value of 0.98% as a percentage. In the passage between 2018 and 2019 the value of the employment rate in Northern Italy grew from an amount equal to 72.20% up to a value equal to 72.90% or equal to an absolute value of 0.70 units and percentage equal to 0.97%. Overall in the period between 2015 and 2019 the value of the employment rate in Northern Italy increased by an amount equal to 3.50 points in absolute value equal to a value of 5.04%.

The trend of the employment rate in Central Italy in the 2015-2019 period. The employment rate in central Italy grew between 2015 and 2016 by an amount equal to 65.80% up to a value equal to 66.50% or equal to a variation of 0.70 units equal to an amount of 1.065. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the employment rate in central Italy went from an amount equal to 66.50% up to a value equal to 67.20% or equal to a value of 0.70 units equal to a value of 1.05%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the employment rate in Central Italy grew from an amount of 67.20% to a value of 67.80% or a change equal to a value of 0.60 units in absolute value and equal to 0.89% in percentage value. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the employment rate in central Italy grew from an amount of 67.80% to a value of 68.30%. Overall between

2015 and 2019 the value of the employment rate in Central Italy grew by an amount equal to 2.50 units, equal to a growth of 3.80%.

The trend of the employment rate in Southern Italy in the 2015-2019 period. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the employment rate increased from an amount of 46.10% up to a value of 47.00% or equal to a variation of 0.90 units equal to a value of 1 , 95%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the employment rate in the South increased from a value of 47.00% to a value of 47.705 or equal to a variation of 0.70 units in absolute value and equal to an amount of 1.49% in percentage value. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the employment rate in the South went from an amount equal to 47.70% up to a value equal to 48.20% or equal to a variation of 0.50 units equal to an amount of 1.05%. Between 2018 and 2019, the occupancy rate increased from an amount of 48.20% to a value of 48.50%.

Conclusions. The value of the employment rate tends to grow in Northern Italy, in Central Italy, in the South and in Italy in general. However, the employment rate in the South is significantly lower than the employment rates in the North, the Center and also with respect to the national figure. On average, in the period between 2015 and 2019, the employment rate in the South was 23.82% lower than the corresponding value in Northern Italy, 19.62% lower than the employment rate in the center and 14.68 % lower than the national value. Sure someone will say that there is black employment. However, it should be considered that the shadow economy also grows in relation to the emerged economy. If the formal economy is compromised, the informal economy also suffers. The idea that there are hidden economic forces in the South that can actually "overturn" the results is to be rejected. In fact, the same perhaps "*hidden*" ones also exist in other areas of the country, where, being able to count on more productive emerged economies, they have greater capacity for manifestation. For the South, it is therefore necessary to strengthen the economy that has emerged through the traditional association between work and business in a favorable institutional climate with a capable ruling class inspired by a public mission even if operating in the private sector.

Variazione assoluta tasso di occupazione 2004-2019.

Rank	Regioni	2004-2019
1	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 5,5
2	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ 5,4
3	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 4,9
4	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 4,8
5	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 4,4
6	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 4,2
7	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 3,9
8	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 3,8
9	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 3,7
10	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 2,9
11	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 2,7
12	<i>Molise</i>	★ 2,1
13	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 2
14	<i>Marche</i>	★ 1,9
15	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 1,7
16	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 1,3
17	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 1,2
18	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -2,6
19	<i>Campania</i>	★ -4,2
20	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -5,4

Variazione assoluta del tasso di occupazione tra il 2004 ed il 2019. Fonte: Istat.

Variazione del tasso di occupazione per macro-aree tra il 2004 ed il 2019. Fonte: Istat.

Tasso di occupazione nelle regioni italiane 2019. Istat.

Rank	Regione	Tasso di occupazione
1	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ 76,6
2	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 75,4
3	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ 73,5
4	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 73,4
5	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 72,6
6	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 71,7
7	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 71,3
8	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 70,8
9	<i>Marche</i>	★ 69,8
10	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 69,3
11	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 67,7
12	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 65,7
13	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 62,5
14	<i>Molise</i>	★ 58,6
15	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 57,3
16	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 54,8
17	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 50,2
18	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 45,3
19	<i>Campania</i>	★ 45,2
20	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 44,5

Differenziale tra il tasso di occupazione del mezzogiorno, del Nord, del Centro e dell'Italia

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	media
Mezzogiorno-Nord	-23,30	-23,60	-23,80	-24,00	-24,40	-23,82
Mezzogiorno-Centro	-19,70	-19,50	-19,50	-19,60	-19,80	-19,62
Mezzogiorno-Italia	-14,40	-14,60	-14,60	-14,80	-15,00	-14,68

Tasso di Occupazione nelle Regioni Italiane. Fonte: Istat, 2019.

Tasso di occupazione nelle regioni italiane. Fonte: Istat, 2019

Andamento del tasso di occupazione. Fonte: Istat

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2015-2019
Nord	★ 69,40	★ 70,60	★ 71,50	★ 72,20	★ 72,90	
Variazione assoluta		☆ 1,20	☆ 0,90	☆ 0,70	☆ 0,70	☆ 3,50
Variazione percentuale		☆ 1,73	☆ 1,27	☆ 0,98	☆ 0,97	☆ 5,04
Centro	★ 65,80	★ 66,50	★ 67,20	★ 67,80	★ 68,30	
Variazione assoluta		☆ 0,70	☆ 0,70	☆ 0,60	☆ 0,50	☆ 2,50
Variazione percentuale		☆ 1,06	☆ 1,05	☆ 0,89	☆ 0,74	☆ 3,80
Mezzogiorno	★ 46,10	★ 47,00	★ 47,70	★ 48,20	★ 48,50	
Variazione assoluta		☆ 0,90	☆ 0,70	☆ 0,50	☆ 0,30	☆ 2,40
Variazione percentuale		☆ 1,95	☆ 1,49	☆ 1,05	☆ 0,62	☆ 5,21
Italia	★ 60,50	★ 61,60	★ 62,30	★ 63,00	★ 63,50	
Variazione assoluta		☆ 1,10	☆ 0,70	☆ 0,70	☆ 0,50	☆ 3,00
Variazione percentuale		☆ 1,82	☆ 1,14	☆ 1,12	☆ 0,79	☆ 4,96

Tasso di occupazione delle regioni Italiane nel periodo 2004-2019. Fonte: Istat

